

THE ROLE OF THE FRUIT AND VEGETABLE SECTOR IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN, WAYS OF USING MARKETING PRINCIPLES IN THE PROCESSES OF CULTIVATION, STORAGE, PROCESSING AND SALES

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Annotation: by ensuring the sustainable development of fruit and vegetable growing in the long term and increasing the efficiency of the network, it will be possible to meet the demand for food products, ensure its safety, expand the geography of exports and increase the living conditions of our people.

Keywords: fruit and vegetable, cluster.

Analysis of the experience of developed countries in the cultivation, storage, processing and export of fruit and vegetable products shows that there is a need to develop cooperation and clusters of manufacturers of these products.

It is known that the existing natural and climatic conditions in our country allow the sustainable development of agricultural products, in particular, fruit and vegetable growing. The president and the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan pays great attention to the development of fruit and vegetable growing as a priority in the process of transition of the industry to market relations. After all, the fact that a significant part of the country's foreign exchange earnings is being formed due to the sale of fruit and vegetable products in foreign markets also testifies to the priority of radical reform and rapid development of the industry.

In particular, in recent years, a number of decrees and resolutions have been adopted. These include PF-5388 decrees of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2018 "on additional measures for the rapid development of fruit and vegetable growing in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and PP-5853 "on additional measures to improve the efficiency of the release of fruit and vegetable products to foreign markets" dated October 17, 2018 "on approval of the strategy of agricultural development, Decisions of PP-4239 of March 14, 2019 "on measures for the development of agricultural cooperation in the field of fruit and vegetable growing" can be cited.

The role of the myeva-vegetable growing network in the economy of Uzbekistan
In general, the economic reforms carried out in the network make it possible to solve the following economic and social issues:

in the economic issue-fruit and vegetable production is one of the main incomes of the population in rural areas, accounting for 32.2% of the total produced

agricultural products (8.7% of the country's gross domestic product). It has its direct impact on the development of a number of industries. Also, this network occupies the main places in the country's agricultural exports;

in the social issue-the effectiveness of the sustainable development of fruit and vegetable growing, has a direct impact not only on the standard of living of the rural population, but also on increasing the social well-being of all the inhabitants of the country.

As a result, the ultimate goal of these reforms is to ensure food security in the country, which is clearly reflected in the positive results of economic reforms carried out in all processes of development of New Uzbekistan and reflects the increase in the standard of living of the population.

Alternative "... the fact that effective market mechanisms have not been systematically established in the field, especially in the development of fruit and vegetable growing and viticulture, insufficient scientific approach leads to the fact that the existing capabilities of the network are not fully used. It is estimated that there is a possibility of earning 7 times more than grapes, 6 times more than cherries, 5 times more than nuts, compared to cotton raw materials grown on an area of 1 hectare" (1).

It is also impossible to say that the existing opportunities are fully used in the processing, storage and export of these products. President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev noted "" today, only 15% of the fruits and vegetables grown in our country are processed and 8% are exported. Especially in Syrdarya, Jizzakh, Khorezm, Kashkadarya and Tashkent regions, these indicators still remain low. Is it in line with our capacity and capacity that 860,000 tons or 620 million dollars of fruit and vegetable exports will be exported this year? No, Of course! There are no techniques that, based on the experience of developed countries, can process gardens and vineyards, plant and harvest seeds of vegetables and potatoes. Work on the supply of fuel and lubricants, mineral fertilizers, seeds to farms, the fight against diseases and pests is not organized at the required level" (2)

Information on the cultivation of fruit and vegetable products

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Processing and storage of fruit and vegetable products Processing fruit and vegetable products without dying off, prolonging seasonality is also one of the unused possibilities. The abundance of the assortment wet fruits stored in the novelty will prevent the cost this type of product in the markets from artificially rising every year in the winter-spring season, and will have a positive effect on the social protection of the population, without the need for imports of related

products in the winter season.

One of the highest factors in the development of competitive product production and improvement of its assortment structure is the implementation of the preparation of a wide range of nutritional supplements based on the processing of the reserves of natural raw materials available in our region. For example, sweet snacks drinks are prepared using artificial raw materials (nastoyka, ekstrats), the main part of which is brought at the expense of foreign currency from the outside. However, the potential of existing raw materials in our republic, competitive, natural pure nutritional additives that can be obtained on the basis of processing wet fruits, the raw material base can reveal dozens of new facets of the assortment category of good drinks. At the same time, in the regions, the opportunity can be created to restore the performance of hundreds of enterprises for the production of snacks of various capacities without foreign exchange funds for imported raw materials.

According to the indicator of the result of the analysis, the year-by-year increase in the volumes of fruit and vegetable products requires the elimination of a number of problems and shortcomings in the storage and processing network,

the implementation of a radical turn in the reform of the industry with the widespread use of modern innovative, resource-saving digital technologies. In particular:

- in relation to the total production volumes in the Republic, 18.9% of fruits, 5.6% of vegetables and melons, 9.5% of grapes are processed at industrial enterprises;
- the level of supply of refrigerants for storage of grown fruits and vegetables in the regions is 3.7 percent (refrigeration storage facilities are provided with products for only 20-22% during the year);
- most of the existing coolers are morally outdated, not technologically updated, modern technology and digital innovative developments have not been implemented to the proper extent;
- requires an innovative approach to the issue of training qualified personnel for the industry. With the ability to work with advanced experienced modern equipment, insufficient attention is paid to the training of specialists in the field of processing, storage;
- there is no systematic approach to issues of adequate supply of products of modern and technological requirements and volumes of storage and processing enterprises;
- the transport and logistics sector is lagging behind the demand of the time;
- in recent years, the maintenance of fruit and vegetable growing has been carried out on the basis of intensive technology. The result is an increase in seed prices, lower incomes of the rural population, as well as the use of mineral fertilizers, chemicals (255 thousand tons of phosphorus for fruit and vegetable cultivation, 290 thousand tons of nitrogen fertilizer are not enough), the use of heavy machinery, deterioration of the quality of land resources, violation of the ecological balance.

Therefore, according to the analysis and data of the UN organization in the field of food and agriculture (FAO), the volume of losses in the collection, transportation and storage of fruit and vegetable products is up to 22-45 percent, and waste is 12-18 percent.

Another important issue is that the activities of information and consulting centers and digital technologies that provide customers with the necessary information about the products grown in the regions have not been established. In addition, the problem of sorting, processing, packaging and sending products to buyers remains that the existing problems of transport and logistics have not been solved so far in the Republic.

As a reference:

The demand for organic products is growing in the world. In European and Asian countries, the buyer pays more for ready-made certified organic products. Our fruit and vegetable products are naturally organic, but most are not certified by an appropriate certification organization. Due to this, the agricultural products of Uzbekistan are being re-exported ready or processed according to international requirements established through third countries.

International experience

In developed countries, 2-5% of labor resources work, and in most less civilized countries, up to 90% work in the agricultural sector. In developing countries, agricultural production plays a much larger role than in developed countries. The weight of Agriculture in the gross domestic product is on average 22 percent in developing countries and 4 percent in developed countries. In developing countries, more than half of the agricultural products grown in developed countries are grown. UN experts believe that in order to solve the food problem every year, it is required to increase its volume by 6 percent.

According to the UN organization in the field of food and agriculture (FAO), sales of dried nuts and fruits in Europe amounted to 11 billion euros, and dried vegetables-more than 8 billion euros. The experience of new participants, such as Vietnam, has shown that if handled according to the right strategy, there will be an opportunity to export a product worth more than 1 billion euros a year.

Judging by the analyzes, the yield in the garden and vineyards in our country is very low. For example, in countries such as the USA, China, Italy, France, where agriculture is developed, 80-120 tons are harvested from one hectare of intensive garden, up to 140 tons from some fruits, 10-30 tons per hectare are harvested in our country, and 4-5 tons of products are obtained from traditional garden-vineyards. This is certainly an economically ineffective agriculture.

Recommended measures for the sustainable development of the fruit and vegetable sector

first of all, the modernization, renewal of the fruit and vegetable sector, the development and implementation of measures to ensure the competitiveness of manufactured products, which give a strong impetus to the sustainable development of the industry;

secondly, as a result of the increased dependence of the consumer market of the countries of the world on imports, ensuring the safety of food products, improving the mechanism of state support and management of the agrarian sector;

thirdly, due to the fact that from year to year there is a shortage of Water Resources, the limitation of the possibility of efficient use of irrigated land is a

special emphasis on the issue of using advanced methods of irrigation based on innovative technologies, in particular, the widespread introduction of drip irrigation;

fourthly, within the factors affecting the sustainable development of fruit and vegetable growing, the deep analysis of the capabilities and results achieved by farmers and agricultural enterprises in economic, technological, legal and other fields, and the implementation of existing scientific and innovative opportunities through the elimination of identified shortcomings;

fifth, the adoption of programs that provide for filling the place of fruit and vegetable products imported into the country in order to ensure the needs of the population at the expense of the full and effective use of our domestic capabilities, etc.

Also, the analysis of the experience of developed countries in the cultivation, storage, processing and export of fruit and vegetable products shows that there is a need to develop cooperation and clusters of manufacturers of these products.

The growth of the fruit and vegetable sector from the economic side should not be due to the further expansion of the use of existing internal resources, but to the introduction of a competitive production cooperation and cluster system that meets the requirements of the time in terms of quality of products.

Proposals to further support the fruit and vegetable growing network in Uzbekistan

Based on the above analysis, in the sustainable development of the industry in the conditions of Uzbekistan, it is considered appropriate to attach importance to:

- further strengthening financial incentives for the activities of model enterprises operating in rural areas, specializing directly in the storage and

processing of agricultural products in an innovative resource-saving way, introducing tax, customs and other benefits to them;

- to increase the preparation, storage and processing of agricultural raw materials products grown on the basis of the development of compact and small branches of industrial enterprises in each rural area of the Republic, as well as economic incentives for activities aimed at the production of marketable, competitive finished products to the domestic and foreign markets (currency allocation, preferential taxation, credit allocation, etc.);

-organize export-credit organizations or upload the solution of these issues to the responsible ministry and office in order to provide the entrepreneur with comprehensive practical assistance in matters of credit allocation, insurance, foreign markets prior to the export process, "geographical, economic, financial and quality risks", transport and logistics, obtaining relevant certificates, food security (HASSP) and standard, to promote participation in international exhibitions and fairs;

- Organization of multidisciplinary agrolological complexes "Agropark" and "Agrosanoat" based on digital innovative technologies in all possible convenient places. All conditions have been created in this complex, that is, the creation of a system of all processes, from product sales, storage, processing, packaging, biolaboratory service, standardization and export;

- Introduction of the "fruit and vegetable clinic" service;

-development of legal regulatory and technical documentation regulating the requirements for the quality and safety of fruits and vegetables and processed products.

Conclusion

At the present stage of the reforms carried out in our country, the implementation of these measures will ensure the sustainable development of fruit and vegetable growing in the long term, increase the efficiency of the network, meet the demand for food products, ensure its safety, expand the geography of exports and increase the living conditions of our people.

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